

Microwave-assisted Knoevenagel condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with aldehydes in solvent-free condition

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Manuscript received 16 September 2002, revised 1 April 2003, accepted 5 May 2003

Piperazine has been used successfully as a catalyst for the Knoevenagel condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate and aromatic aldehydes along with the rate enhancement by microwave irradiation under solvent-free condition.

Knoevenagel condensation is one of the basic reactions in organic chemistry for its significant synthetic utility in carbon-carbon bond formation, which is a pivotal process in organic synthesis¹. Various catalysts have been known to effect the Knoevenagel condensation². Microwave radiation³ is widely used in chemical reaction enhancement with formation of cleaner products and operational simplicity. Another interest has recently been focused to avoid the use of organic solvent, which leads to organic waste, which is detrimental to environment⁴.

In continuation of our ongoing programme⁵ to carry out reaction in solvent-free condition under microwave irradiation, we have exploited microwave radiation for enhancement of reaction rate of Knoevenagel condensation between ethyl cyanoacetate and several aromatic aldehydes in the presence of piperazine under solvent-free condition (Scheme 1). Piperazine is an efficient catalyst in the Knoevenagel condensation with the yield of 83–98% within 3–20 min (Table 1). For the aldehydes (entries 5–9) having two and three electron-donating substituents in aromatic ring appear to retard the rate of reaction due to inactivation of aldehyde group. Although only single geometric isomers were obtained in all cases, the unambiguous stereochemical assignment could not readily be made.

Scheme 1

In conclusion, we have demonstrated a solvent-free Knoevenagel condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with aromatic aldehydes under microwave irradiation even with deactivated aldehydes in a very short time with excellent yields.

Table 1. Microwave-assisted Knoevenagel condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate and aromatic aldehyde under solvent-free conditions using piperazine as catalyst

Entry no.	Ar	Time min	Product yield %	M.p. °C
1		4	90	48
2		3	98	170
3		3	95	130
4		10	85	88
5		12	88	96
6		10	89	100
7		12	92	130
8		15	86	156
9		20	87	72
10		3	83	94

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary on an electrically heated metal block and are uncorrected. IR spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR-RXI spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a FT NMR Bruker AM 300L (300 MHz) spectrometer and reported in ppm. The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (BPL-SANYO, BMO-700T, 2450 MHz, 1200 W).

General procedure : A mixture of the aldehyde (1 mmol), ethyl cyanoacetate (1 mmol) and piperazine (1 mmol) was taken in a 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask fitted with a funnel as a loose top upon which a round-bottomed flask containing ice was placed to serve as a condenser. It was then placed in an alumina bath (heat sink) inside the microwave oven operating at medium power level (600 W) for the specified time. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC) the product was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 10 ml). The solvent layer was washed with sodium metabisulfite and brine and dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. After removal of the solvent the product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., U.G.C., New Delhi, and University of Calcutta, for providing financial support.

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